

The Effect of Training Program on Nurses' Knowledge and Practices Regarding Nursing Care of Children with Type-I Diabetes Mellitus in Wad Medani Pediatrics Teaching Hospital Gezira State, Sudan

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Abstract

Type-1 diabetes is an autoimmune disease that originate when very little or no insulin is produced by the islets of Langerhans in the pancreas. Untreated, diabetes can cause many complications. Nurses are in a key position to disseminate knowledge and provide proper nursing care resulting in control of the disease and prevent complications. This study was conducted in Pediatrics Teaching Hospital Gezira State, Sudan. This study aimed at assessing the effect of the training program on nurse's knowledge and practice regarding nursing care of children with type-1 diabetes mellitus. training program was done to assist nurses in the Pediatric Teaching Hospital knowledge and skills need in caring of infant with type-1 diabetes mellitus. The program package contains sex session with different learning objectives and use many different teaching techniques methods include lecture, practical, audio visual aids and demonstration. Every session with different title around the diabetic knowledge. Data analysis was performed by using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version (22). The results of nurse knowledge regarding definition of diabetes for correct answer in post-intervention were highly increased in percentage. Also The results of nurse knowledge regarding definition of insulin for correct answer in post-intervention were highly increased in percentage for all questions. The results of nurse knowledge regarding definition of diabetes, insulin and combination insulin products for correct answer in post-intervention were highly increased in percentage. The study concluded that results of nurse knowledge regarding definition of diabetes, insulin and combination insulin products for correct answer in post-intervention were highly increased in percentage. The study recommended that periodic training program on care of children with type-1 diabetes mellitus must be conducted and log book must be design and available for nurses in the hospitals.

Introduction

Type-1 diabetes make up an estimated 10–15% of all diabetes cases or 11–22 million cases worldwide.

Symptoms can begin at any age, but onset is most common in children, with diagnoses slightly more common in 5 to 7 year olds, and much more common

More Information

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around the age of puberty type-1 diabetics are also at increased risk of rheumatoid arthritis, lupus. Conversely, complex autoimmune syndromes caused by mutation in the immunity-related genes [1]. Diabetes is diagnosed annually in the general population. Conditions or situations known to exacerbate glucose/insulin imbalance include previously undiagnosed or newly diagnosed type 1 diabetes; food intake in excess of available associated with illness, infection, trauma, or emotional distress. Type-1 diabetes, can be complicated by instability and diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA). The knowledge should be receiving from physician or nurse of the nature of diabetes and its potential acute and chronic hazards and how they can be recognized early and prevented or treated [2]. Diabetes is a silent disease, many sufferers become aware that they have diabetes only when they develop one of its life-threatening complications. Patients' knowledge of diabetes mellitus can assist in early detection of the disease and reduce the incidence of complications. Levels of knowledge about diabetes among high risk population and among those who suffer from the disease are unknown, but more knowledge is associated with better outcomes [3]. Low diabetes knowledge was significantly associated with female gender and could be a risk factor for development of diabetes-related complications. The areas of knowledge gaps need to be addressed in diabetes education as they might influence the development of diabetes-related complications. The information demonstrates the prevalence of diabetes, one of the fastest-growing health problem in the World, which is reaching epidemic proportion in some regions, as consequence of life-style, lack of exercise, unhealthy diet, obesity and overweight. People throughout the World are encouraged to learn about risks and warning signs of diabetes, to take actions to prevent the disease and seek healthcare in case they develop diabetes [4].

Materials and Methods

Ethical Consideration

Permission from managers and matrons of *Wad Medan* Pediatric hospital was made through official letters.

Study Design

This an intervention cross sectional hospital-based study

Study Area

The study was conducted in *Wad Medani* Pediatric Teaching Hospital in *Wad Medani* Town, Gezira State, Sudan. The *Wad Medani* Pediatric Teaching Hospital receives the patients from the whole State and the neighboring States *Algardarif* and *Sinnar*.

Study Population

Study population were nurses who were working in Pediatric Teaching Hospital during the period of the study from (July 2018 to July 2021).

Inclusion criteria

All the nurses working in neonatal care units in pediatric teaching hospital during the period of

Exclusion criteria

1. Nurses who are working in other setting.
2. Nurses under training.
3. Nursing students

Sample size

All available nurses their number (80) who were working in Pediatric Teaching Hospital.

Phases of intervention

The intervention divided into two phases one pre intervention second post intervention both of them targeting the nurse knowledge.

Pre intervention phase

A Pilot study was done on a sample of seven nurses in an effort to test the validity and feasibility of the questionnaire instrument.

Post intervention program:

A post-test was made using a questionnaire, to evaluate the effect of program on nurses' knowledge regarding care of infant with type one diabetes mellitus.

The training program

The aim of training program to assist nurses in the Pediatric Teaching Hospital knowledge and skills need in caring of infant with type-1 diabetes mellitus. The program package contains sex session with different learning objectives and use many different teaching techniques methods include lecture, practical, audio visual aids and demonstration. Every session with different title around the diabetic knowledge.

Data analysis

The data were analyzed using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version (23), results were presented in frequencies and percentages in Tables.

Results and Discussion

The results of nurse knowledge regarding definition of diabetic for correct answer in post-intervention were highly increased in percentage range between (76.75 to 98.75 %) for correct answer compared to pre intervention which were range between (38.75 to 63.75 %, for eleven questions Table (1). These results are in agreements with results of [5], they stated that the nurses' knowledge regarding definition of diabetes risk factors, and common consequence of hyperglycemia improved after the training program. (38.75%, 43.75% and 40%) of the study sample responses with correct answers regarding symptoms of hypoglycemia, and signs and symptoms of diabetic ketoacidosis pre intervention raises to (88.75%, 97.5% and 83.75%) after pre intervention. The results of nurse knowledge regarding definition of insulin for correct answer in post-intervention were highly increased in percentage range between (91.25 to 81.25 %) for correct answer compared to pre intervention which

were range between (63.25 to 52.5 %, for eleven questions Table (2) These results are in the opposite to results of [6], they stated that nurses had adequate knowledge regarding Definition of Insulin, Side effects and Nursing Assessment. Results of combination of insulin products were ranging between (95.00 to 77.75 %) for correct answer in post-intervention compared to

correct answer in pre-intervention which range between (35.00 to 47.50 %) for all questions Table (3) These results are agree with the results of [6], they stated that nurses need training program to enhance their skills regarding care of children with type 1 diabetes mellitus.

Table 1: Results of Nurse Knowledge Regarding Definition of Diabetes for Pre and Post Intervention

Nurses' knowledge regarding	Pre intervention				Post intervention				Total	
	Correct answers		Incorrect answers		Correct answers		Incorrect answers			
	NO	%	39	%	NO	%	NO	%	NO	%
Definition of Diabetes	41	51.25	39	48.75	79	98.75	1	1.25	80	100
The risk factors for diabetes.	32	40	48	60	61	76.25	19	23.75	80	100
Types of diabetes	35	43.75	45	56.25	70	88.5	10	12.5	80	100
Hypoglycemia	33	41.25	47	58.75	74	92.5	6	7.5	80	100
Symptoms of Hypoglycemia	31	38.75	49	61.25	71	88.75	9	11.25	80	100
symptoms of hyperglycemia	35	43.75	45	56.25	78	97.5	2	2.5	80	100
consequence of hyperglycemia	51	63.75	29	36.25	60	75	20	25	80	100
Complications	42	52.5	38	47.5	75	93.75	5	6.25	80	100
Symptoms of ketoacidosis	34	42.5	46	57.5	69	86.25	11	13.75	80	100
Signs and symptoms of diabetic ketoacidosis	32	40	48	60	67	83.75	13	16.25	80	100
Mean total	37	46.25	43	53.75	70	87.5	10	12.5		

Table 2: Results of Nurse Knowledge Regarding Definition of Insulin for Pre and Post Intervention

Nurses' knowledge regarding	Pre intervention				Post intervention				Total	
	Correct answers		Incorrect answers		Correct answers		Incorrect answers			
	NO	%	NO	%	NO	%	NO	%	NO	%
Definition of Insulin	35	43.75	45	56.25	70	87.5	10	12.5	80	100
Other medication	32	40	48	60	73	91.25	7	8.75	80	100
Indication	38	47.5	42	52.5	65	81.25	15	18.75	80	100
Side effects	42	52.5	38	47.5	70	87.5	10	12.5	80	100
Allergy to Insulin products	38	47.5	42	52.5	72	90	8	10	80	100
Principles	39	48.75	41	51.25	70	87.5	10	12.5	80	100
Nursing Assessment	33	41.25	47	58.75	68	85	12	15	80	100
common types of insulin	29	36.25	51	63.75	66	82.5	14	17.5	80	100
Fast-acting	33	41.25	47	58.75	66	82.5	14	17.5	80	100
Short-acting	32	40	48	60	68	85	12	15	80	100
Intermediate-acting	32	40	48	60	65	81.25	15	18.75	80	100
Long-acting	36	45	44	55	69	86.25	11	13.75	80	100
Ultra-long acting	34	42.5	46	57.5	68	85	12	15	80	100
Mean total	34	42.5	46	57.5	68	85	12	15		

Conclusion

The results of nurse knowledge regarding definition of diabetes, insulin and combination insulin products for correct answer in post-intervention were highly increased in percentage

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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